

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE TOTAL CONTENT OF POLYPHENOLS IN EXTRUDED GRAIN MIXTURES WITH THE ADDITION OF POMACE FROM FOOD PRODUCTION

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Abstract

Vegetable foods are rich not only in vitamins, fiber, healthy fats, but also contain another class of useful substances - polyphenols. Once in the human body, they have a positive effect on all organs and life processes. These compounds have antioxidant activity, protecting our body from harmful environmental factors. The article presents data on the content of polyphenols in extruded grain products with the addition of pomace from food production.

Keywords: polyphenols, extruded products, addition of pomace from food production.

1. Introduction

Scientists have long expressed the opinion that the deterioration of public health in the world is directly related to the deterioration of the quality of nutrition. Most people don't bother to think about what they eat? Meanwhile, it is nutrition that is the factor that either worsens or improves human health every day.

In modern life, a person is constantly exposed to stress and unfavorable ecology, while not everyone eats properly and fully, which affects the functioning of the body. Thus, in modern conditions of life, toxic compounds (free radicals) accumulate in the human body, which in large quantities can adversely affect the state of human health. The most urgent solution to this problem is the use of antioxidants, which allow in a safe way to significantly slow down the oxidation processes in the body, as well as the formation of free radicals, thereby increasing the level of antioxidant protection of the body.

Antioxidants are phenolic acids, flavonoids, coumarins, polyphenols, phytates, terpenes, carotenoids, tocopherols.

Antioxidants are of natural origin and received in the human body from food, primarily from vegetables and fruits.

Scientific studies have shown that one of the reasons why vegetable foods are good for the human body is the presence of polyphenols in them. Currently, there are more than 8,000 varieties of polyphenols.

Due to the wide variety of polyphenols and the plants that contain them, these compounds are divided according to the source of origin, the function of the polyphenols, and their chemical structure. The main ones are flavonoids, phenolic acids, stilbenes and lignans.

Some scientists suggest that regular consumption of vegetable foods with high content of polyphenols,

especially flavonoids, may reduce the risk of blood clots and plaques, reduce inflammation, reduce blood pressure and the risk of heart attacks, slow the development of cancer, and help control blood sugar levels. Thus, for the prevention of these diseases, it is necessary to create new types of products with a high content of antioxidants.

One of the modern processes of the production of new generation products is extrusion, which makes it possible to obtain products enriched with biologically active components.

The purpose of this work is to determine the content of polyphenols in extruded products based on cereals with the addition of pomace from food production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The following materials were used to produce samples of extruded products:

- grains: wheat and corn;
- pomace from apples, tomatoes, grape varieties: Muscat, Cabernet, Codrinsky and Sauvignon obtained in the production of juices;
- reagents: ethanol, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, tannin.

2.2 Obtaining extruded products

Samples of extruded products were obtained on an experimental extruder E-150 installed at the "Polikom-Prim" enterprise.

Production scheme:

1. The pomace was subjected to convection drying at a temperature of 55-60°C, then crushed to a size of 1-2 mm and 20% of the main raw material was added to the mixture for extrusion.

2. According to the technological process, a mixture of grains and pomace powders was humidified to 15-16% and then extruded under the following process parameters (Table 1).

Table 1.

Parameters of the technological process for the production of polycomponent extruded products

Nr.	Raw material	Temperature, °C	Pressure, atm.	Time, s.	Humidity of mixture, %
1	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from apples	110-115	26-30	14-16	15,6
2	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from apples	90-100	24-26	13-16	15,7
3	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Muscat	95-105	25-27	16-18	15,4
4	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Muscat	100-110	25-27	15-18	15,3
5	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Sauvignon	110-120	28-30	17-20	15,6
6	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Sauvignon	100-105	25-27	15-17	15,1
7	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Cabernet	100-110	26-28	15-18	15,8
8	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Cabernet	100-105	25-27	15-17	15,1
9	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Codrinsky	105-115	27-30	17-20	15,7
10	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Codrinsky	90-100	25-27	16-18	15,3

In the production of an experimental lot 5 kg of each mixture was used. First, the extruder was heated to a temperature of 140-150°C.

From the data in Table 1 it follows that the temperature of raw material processing in the extruder varies from 90 °C to 120°C. The production time for extruded products is from 13sec to 20 sec. Depending on the composition of the mixture, the pressure was 24–30 atm.

2.3 Determination of total polyphenols

Polyphenols were determined both in raw materials and in extruded products. The total content of polyphenols in raw materials and extruded products was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, consisting of a mixture of phosphotungstic and phosphomolybdic acids.

Tannin in this study is used to construct a calibration graph.

For analysis, the product was extracted with a 70% alcohol solution. The weight of the sample of the product is 2-5 g with 100 ml of a 70% alcohol solution, thoroughly triturated and left for 10 minutes. Then take 1-5 ml of the extract, combine with 1-5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu, add 10 ml of 20% Na₂CO₃, mix the mixture and incubate for 30 minutes in the dark. After this time, the sample is analyzed in a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of $\alpha=630$ nm.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Polyphenol content of raw materials and extruded products

3.1.1 Determination of polyphenols in pomace and grain powders was carried out in their extracts.

First, the extraction solution was chosen. For this ethyl alcohol 30% and 70%, water 90°C, ethyl alcohol 30% + 1g citric acid were used.

The content of polyphenols in raw materials in different extraction solutions is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

The content of polyphenols in raw materials in different extraction solutions

Nr.	Raw material	Content of polyphenols, mg/100 g			
		70% ethyl alcohol	30 % ethyl alcohol	30 % ethyl alcohol +1g. citric acid	Water 90 °C
1	Pomace powders from tomatoes	680	680	760	680
2	Pomace powders from apples	252	246	248	200
3	Pomace powders from grape Cabernet	662	416	380	200
4	Wheat	330	80	-	100
5	Corn	294	77	-	97

As can be seen from table 2, the extraction of polyphenols takes place more intensively in a solution of 70% ethyl alcohol. Further extraction of all products was carried out in this solution.

3.1.2 The content of polyphenols in raw materials are presented in table 3

Table 3.

Content of polyphenols in raw materials

Nr.	Raw material	Content of polyphenols, mg/100 g of extract
1	Wheat	330
2	Corn	294
3	Pomace powders from tomatoes	680
4	Pomace powders from apples	252
5	Pomace powders from grape Muscat	5340
6	Pomace powders from grape Codrinsky	5100
7	Pomace powders from grape Cabernet	662
8	Pomace powders from grape Sauvignon	3440

At the analyses of the results of the content of polyphenols in the studied pomace powders in Table 3, it was found that the highest content of polyphenols is on the pomace powder from grape and constitute 3440-5340 mg/100g.

The content of polyphenols in grains is only 294-330 mg/100g.

3.1.3 The content of polyphenols in extruded products is shown in Table 4.

Table 4.

Content of polyphenols in extruded products

№	Raw material	Content of polyphenols, mg/100 g of extract
1	Corn + 20 % Pomace powders from apples	286
2	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Sauvignon	923
3	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Muscat	1303
4	Corn + 20 % Pomace powders from grape Cabernet	367
5	Corn + 20 % pomace powders from grape Kodrinsky	1255
6	Wheat + 20 % Pomace powders from apples	314
7	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Sauvignon	952
8	Wheat + 20 % pomace powders from grape Muscat	1332

Analysis of the data in Table 4 allows us to conclude that the addition of 20% pomace powder to grains increases the content of polyphenols in grain extrudates up to 300%. For example, when adding pomace powders from grape Muscat, both wheat extrudate and corn extrudate, the content of polyphenols was 1332 mg/100 g and 1303 mg/100g respectively.

Conclusions

1. Expanded the range of extruded products with the addition of pomace powders from: apples, grapes and tomatoes, which allows the use of secondary resources of the canning and wine industry

2. New types of products with increased biological value have been obtained, namely with a high content of polyphenols, which classifies them as preventive products

3. The highest content of polyphenols is observed in polycomponent extrudates based on grains and 20% powder from pomace powders from grape Muscat and pomace powders from grape Kodrinsky.

4. Utilization of secondary resources improves the ecology of the country, and also allows the use of non-waste production.

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